

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners

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ABSTRACT

Reading and reading comprehension are interrelated skills. In order for students to be able to comprehend what they are reading, they also have to develop their skills in identifying main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details. In this context, the goal of this study was to assess the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in preparation for a proposed intervention plan. This study employed a descriptive research design using a self-made test instrument to assess the reading comprehension level of 87 grade 3 learners. The data were statistically analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, and t-test. The results revealed that the participants were mostly males, came from lower-income families, and resided near school. Overall, the reading comprehension skills of grade 3 learners across areas were at the instructional level. When grouped according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance of home to school, the reading comprehension of grade 3 learners were at the instructional level. Further, no significant difference was found in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners across areas when compared according to variable sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school. The study calls for school heads and reading teachers to work together to implement targeted interventions by considering learners' background profiles to address least mastered skills, particularly for learners at the frustration level.

Keywords: Grade 3 Learners, Literacy Skills, Reading Comprehension

How to Cite:

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INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension is a foundational skill crucial for learning, critical thinking, and communication, and difficulties in this area lead to frequent academic challenges (Khalilova, 2023; Snowling et al., 2020). Globally, poor reading comprehension remains a major concern, as reflected in consistently low PISA reading proficiency scores across countries (Luzano et al., 2024). These shortcomings negatively affect students' performance in other subjects and limit future opportunities, prompting educators worldwide to implement various literacy-focused initiatives (Ibrahim, 2024).

The Philippines faces similar difficulties, with DepEd data showing that many Filipino learners continue to struggle with reading comprehension (Villanueva, 2022). Such deficiencies can hinder overall academic achievement and long-term prospects (Hemmings et al., 2019). Although interventions have been introduced, significant gaps remain in understanding the specific factors contributing to poor comprehension among Filipino learners (Bernardo et al., 2021). Research points to multiple causes, including challenges in identifying main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary (Lynch, 2020), and broader influences such as features of the Philippine school system, linguistic factors, and socio-economic conditions (Cabural & Infantado, 2023).

As a public elementary school teacher, the researcher found motivation to research and explore the reading comprehension among grade 3 learners. The study results would equip teachers with comprehensive knowledge on developing intervention plans to address the deficiencies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in a public elementary school of a large-sized division in Central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025 as a basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of identifying the main idea, making inference, understanding vocabulary, determining supporting details; 2) the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and 3) the significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reading is a fundamental skill that elementary learners must master because it supports all other areas of learning; it requires not just decoding text but understanding meaning, enabling students to absorb information accurately (Saonah, 2018; Pratiwi, 2020). However, reading comprehension remains a persistent challenge in many schools and is a major concern for the Department of Education (Velardo & Catoto, 2022). Defined as the ability to extract meaning from text (Hernandez, 2018), comprehension is essential for learning, problem-solving, and academic success. Studies highlight that effective instruction, explicit strategies such as “get the gist” (Shelton, 2020), and strengthened vocabulary development (Santillan & Daenos, 2020) are crucial for improving reading outcomes. Research consistently shows that factors such as socio-economic status (Magnuson, 2015; Chavez & Honesto, 2025; Villados, 2020), home-to-school distance (Pastera, 2024), parental education (Dela Rosa & Paragas, 2024), and linguistic skills all influence learners' comprehension levels. Numerous studies across grade levels reveal that many pupils remain at frustration or instructional levels in comprehension skills—whether in vocabulary, fluency, inferencing, sequencing, or identifying main ideas (Hernandez, 2019; Bohol, 2024; Agabon, 2020; Amorganda, 2024; Sali, 2023).

Given the critical role of reading comprehension in academic achievement and lifelong learning, educators, parents, and communities share responsibility for developing proficient readers (Miñoza & Montero, 2019). Curriculum goals highlight the need to strengthen higher-order thinking and information-processing skills through targeted teaching strategies and interventions (Oclarit & Casinillo, 2021; Tavera & Casinillo, 2020). Studies show mixed results regarding differences in reading skills across sex, income levels, and grade levels, with some finding significant variation (Chavez & Honesto, 2025; Dela Rosa & Paragas, 2024) and others reporting none (Pintero & Cañedo, 2024; Bohol, 2024; Agabon, 2020). Overall, the literature consistently points to widespread comprehension difficulties among elementary learners and emphasizes the urgent need for sustained, evidence-based instructional support to address weaknesses in vocabulary, inferencing, main-idea identification, and other essential components of reading.

Identifying the main idea is essential for understanding and remembering what one reads, as it captures the central point supported by the passage's details (Shelton, 2020). The main idea reflects what the author aims to convey, and the rest of the paragraph functions to explain and support it (Mauli et al., 2018). However, students often struggle to determine the main idea, especially when faced with long, complex sentences or when they have low reading interest, which weakens their overall reading competence (Mauli et al., 2018). Research shows that being able to identify the main idea strengthens comprehension because it helps unify and connect ideas within the text (Dolba et al., 2022; Basali, 2024). Yet many learners still find it difficult to

distinguish general statements from details, leading to confusion and reduced comprehension (Castillo et al., 2019; Vidal, 2022; Sitohang et al., 2021).

Making inferences is another crucial skill in reading comprehension, requiring readers to draw conclusions and integrate information that is not explicitly stated by combining textual clues with background knowledge (Warnidah et al., 2016; Kendeou, McMaster, & Christ, 2016). Research shows that inference ability strongly predicts reading comprehension across developmental stages (Barth et al., 2015) and can be improved through explicit instruction, even within short interventions (Elleman, 2017; Willingham, 2017). Effective strategies include using prior knowledge, creating elaborations, employing graphic organizers, and identifying textual clues (Kendeou et al., 2016). Conversely, students with learning difficulties often struggle with making inferences, hindering their ability to construct meaning from text and engage in higher-order thinking (Hall & Barnes, 2017; De Jesus, 2016; Vidal, 2022). Inferencing is therefore a foundational skill that must be developed early, relying heavily on students' experience and background knowledge (Suraprajit, 2019).

Vocabulary knowledge also plays a critical role in reading comprehension, as understanding word meanings directly impacts a reader's ability to grasp overall text meaning (Mauli et al., 2018). Students with limited vocabulary often struggle with comprehension, become easily frustrated, and miss key details in a passage (Prihatini, 2020; Hart, 2021; Kiew & Shah, 2020). Vocabulary instruction enhances deep reading understanding and equips learners with strategies for decoding, inferring meaning, and using context clues (Harmon & Wood, 2018; Rosado & Caro, 2018). Poor vocabulary—often influenced by poverty, limited exposure, and insufficient instruction—reduces communicative competence and long-term reading success (Mercado, 2020; Cruz, 2015). Because vocabulary develops continuously, learners must engage in varied strategies such as dictionary use, explicit instruction, indirect exposure, and vocabulary-learning strategies to support comprehension and overall communication (Ferrer & Carmen, 2022; Santillan & Daenso, 2020).

Determining supporting details is likewise essential, as these details clarify and provide evidence for the main idea through examples, explanations, and facts (Lestari et al., 2017; Flemming, 2015). Supporting details can appear anywhere within a paragraph depending on its structure and serve to strengthen and develop the topic sentence (Scarry, 2015). Identifying these details allows students to validate the author's argument and enhances comprehension by showing how ideas are connected (Vidal, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design in determining the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in a public elementary school of a large-sized division in Central Philippines for School Year 2024-2025 as a basis for an intervention plan.

According to Aggarwal & Ranganathan (2019), descriptive research is a methodical approach to gathering and analyzing factual data. It is valuable to provide facts on which scientific judgment may be based when assessing the present study. In addition, a descriptive design is appropriate for studies that aim to discover what prevails in the present conditions, practices, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends.

The researcher believes that the descriptive research design is the most suitable for the present study as it involves describing the conditions of things in their present state, practices, beliefs, effects, and factors that influence poor reading comprehension of the learners.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were the 87 grade 3 learners who were officially enrolled during the school year 2024-2025. Since the total number of respondents was manageable, purposive sampling will be used. Ames et al. (2019) defined purposive sampling as a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study.

Instruments

This study employed a researcher-made questionnaire consisting of two parts: the respondents' personal profile (sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school) and a 32-item reading comprehension test divided into four areas—identifying the main idea, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details. Learners were asked to read the directions carefully and select the best answers. To ensure validity—defined as the accuracy of an instrument in measuring what it is intended to measure (Sudaryono et al., 2019)—the instrument underwent face and content validation by three expert validators, all of whom possessed relevant graduate degrees and extensive experience in reading instruction and research. Their recommendations were incorporated into the final version, and the computed validity index of 5.00 indicated excellent validity. Reliability, described as the consistency of measurement across repeated tests with minimal error (Imasuen, 2022), was established through a dry-run test with 30 non-respondent Grade 3 learners, and the results were processed using the Kuder and Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), which assesses internal consistency for dichotomous items (Ikbi, 2021). The computed reliability score of 0.967 fell within the “excellent” range, confirming that the instrument was highly reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother study, the researcher employed the following procedures: a letter of request addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study was submitted for approval. Upon approval, a separate letter will also be given to the school head of the school concerned. The researcher distributed the questionnaires to the target respondents with the assistance of class advisers. A consent form was given to the parents to allow their children to be the subject of the study. The purpose of the study was adequately explained to the learners and the parents by the researcher. The learners' responses in the research questionnaire were anonymous, and the researcher preserved the confidentiality of the learners' data. The questionnaires were administered during the learners' free time so as not to hamper the schedule of classes. Upon the 100% retrieval of the data needed, it will be tallied and presented in tabular form for straightforward interpretation and analysis by the researcher.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 also uses the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners.

Objective No. 2 uses the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 3 uses the comparative analytical scheme and t-test to determine if there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher prioritized the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity to prevent human rights violations during the research process. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents could withdraw without consequences. We informed them about the study's academic purpose. The researcher also obtained parents' consent and respondents' assent to affirm their participation in the study further. Only the researcher(s) had access to the data, ensuring confidentiality. Moreover, during the study, the researcher strictly observed the governing guidelines and policies of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure security measures were in place to protect personal and sensitive information. This commitment to ethical standards fostered trust among participants and enhanced the integrity of the research findings. By adhering to these guidelines, we aimed to uphold the highest level of professionalism in our research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners According to the Areas: Identifying the Main Ideas, Making Inferences, Understanding Vocabulary, and Determining Supporting Details

Reading Comprehension Levels	Mean	Interpretation
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Identifying the Main Ideas	67.67	Instructional Level
Making Inferences	77.30	Instructional Level
Understanding Vocabulary	56.18	Instructional Level
Determining Supporting Details	63.65	Instructional Level

Table 1 reveals the results on the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the areas of identifying the main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details.

In the area of identifying main ideas, the learners obtained a mean score of 67.67, which was interpreted as an instructional level. The result implies that most learners, to some level, can identify the main idea of a sentence or paragraph; they are more likely to comprehend it. However, there are instances when the learners find difficulty determining the main idea because of lengthy sentences, and some learners have average vocabulary skills, causing difficulty sorting out the relationship of words. The learners still need the instructional assistance of teachers to improve their comprehension skills. The result is supported by Sari (2023), revealing that the level of reading proficiency was low in getting the main idea. The learners haven't fully developed the reading skills they need to understand their reading materials. Likewise, Rasonable and Velasco (2023) revealed that the reading competency of the learners in terms of identifying the main ideas and key ideas was fair.

In the area of making inferences, the learners obtained a mean score of 77.30, which was interpreted as an instructional level. The result implies that the learners, to some level, can infer or make conclusions in a given statement. However, there are instances where the learners had difficulties comprehending the text due to having average vocabulary knowledge. This difficulty in making inferences suggests that additional support and targeted instruction may be necessary to enhance their comprehension skills. Agabon (2020) provides support for the results. This study revealed that the learners' comprehension skills in making inferences were at an instructional level. Wardinah (2016) showed that the students' overall difficulty in making inferences in reading narrative passages belonged to the moderate category. Similarly, Soto et al.'s (2019) study stated that deep vocabulary can help a person comprehend a text easily and significantly improve inferential skills. Poor inferential reading comprehension can affect students' performance in school.

In the area of understanding vocabulary, the learners obtained a mean score of 56.18, interpreted as an instructional level. The result implies that the learners have an average vocabulary understanding of the text they read. The learners can identify individual words in text, but do not have a strong foundation in grasping the meanings of words and phrases. Most learners still fall within the fair range, suggesting the need for continued support and intervention in vocabulary development. The findings are supported by Bohol (2024), revealing that the reading comprehension of key stage 2 learners in terms of vocabulary was at the instructional level.

Further, in the area of determining supporting details, the learners obtained a mean score of 63.65, interpreted as an instructional level. The finding implies that the learners can choose the supporting information for the main topic or idea of the sentence or paragraph. However, some learners still have difficulty determining supporting details because of incorrect reading, a lack of vocabulary, and understanding the main idea of reading texts, which becomes an obstacle in reading comprehension. The finding is supported by Lestari et al. (2017) on students' skills in identifying supporting details in reading comprehension. This research found that the students' skill in identifying supporting details in reading text was in the poor category.

Table 2

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Areas of Identifying the Main Ideas, Making Inferences, Understanding Vocabulary, and Determining Supporting Details According to Sex

Items	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Identifying the Main Ideas	67.71	Instructional	67.63	Instructional
Making Inferences	77.08	Instructional	77.56	Instructional
Understanding Vocabulary	55.99	Instructional	56.41	Instructional
Determining Supporting Details	63.28	Instructional	64.10	Instructional

Table 2 reveals the results on the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the areas of identifying the main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details when grouped according to sex.

Analyzing the results, it is evident that there is a slight difference in the mean scores between male and female learners. Female learners obtained better mean scores in making inferences, vocabulary understanding, and determining supporting details than male learners. On the other hand, male learners have higher mean scores in identifying the main ideas of females.

The finding implies that female learners have better reading comprehension skills, particularly in making inferences, vocabulary, and analyzing text. In comparison, male learners may be proficient only at word recognition but have fewer analysis skills. This information indicates that female learners exhibit more inferential thinking skills than males. This skill disparity may suggest that educational strategies could be tailored to enhance male learners' analytical abilities, encouraging a more balanced development of reading comprehension skills across genders. The result indicates that gender should be a constant factor in reading activities. The result aligns with that of Agabon (2021), which revealed that female learners obtained higher ratings on reading comprehension skills than males.

Table 3

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Areas of Identifying the Main Ideas, Making Inferences, Understanding Vocabulary, and Determining Supporting Details According to Average Family Monthly Income

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Identifying the Main Ideas	68.93	Instructional	66.83	Instructional
Making Inferences	77.50	Instructional	77.16	Instructional
Understanding Vocabulary	55.71	Instructional	56.49	Instructional
Determining Supporting Details	63.93	Instructional	63.46	Instructional

Table 3 discloses the results on the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the areas of identifying the main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details when grouped according to average family monthly income.

Evaluating the mean results carefully, it is very clear that there is a little difference in the mean results; in the area of making inferences, learners who belonged to higher-income families obtained better mean scores in the area of identifying the main idea, making inferences, and determining supporting details than learners who belonged to lower-income families. On the other hand, learners from lower-income families obtained better mean scores in the area of understanding vocabulary.

The data imply that learners from lower-income families have an advantage over their counterparts in identifying main ideas, making inferences, and determining supporting details in the text they read. However, learners from higher-income families have a stronger vocabulary foundation than their peers from lower-income families. This suggests that while lower-income learners may excel in comprehension skills, higher-income learners possess a more extensive vocabulary, which can enhance their overall reading proficiency. The contrasting strengths highlight the complex relationship between socio-economic status and literacy development. Many learners face disadvantages associated with low economic status, which are largely beyond their control and make learning more challenging; however, their persistence in learning allows them to perform better in school than their peers from higher-income families.

The finding aligns with that of Villados (2020), who revealed that learners from lower-income families performed significantly better in reading abilities than their counterparts from higher-income families. Likewise, Magnuson (2015) states that socio-economic status has a greater influence on academic productivity or learning at school, including language acquisition or reading proficiency.

Table 4

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Areas of Identifying the Main Ideas, Making Inferences, Understanding Vocabulary, and Determining Supporting Details According to Distance from Home to School

Items	Near		Far	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation

Identifying the Main Ideas	65.63	Instructional	68.86	Instructional
Making Inferences	74.61	Instructional	78.86	Instructional
Understanding Vocabulary	55.08	Instructional	56.82	Instructional
Determining Supporting Details	61.72	Instructional	64.77	Instructional

Table 4 unveils the results on the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the areas of identifying the main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details when grouped according to distance from home to school.

Investigating the table further, learners who lived farther from school obtained higher mean scores in the areas of identifying the main ideas, making inferences, understanding vocabulary, and determining supporting details than learners who lived near school.

The findings imply that learners who live farther from school have better reading comprehension skills than learners who live near school. This is because those who live farther from school have to spend longer hours traveling to school; thus, they spend their time wisely on reading activities at school and home. The finding suggests that it is essential to consider learners' geographical location when conducting school reading activities. This is because long walking distances pose psychological, physical, and health hazards to the learners. The learners suffer from fatigue and poor concentration in class after spending long hours on the road trying to get to and from class.

The finding relates to that of Taiwo (2019), which revealed that walking long distances to and from school daily has a negative impact on students' performance, as it could promote absenteeism and fatigue, leading to a lack of concentration and interest in reading and school activities.

Table 5

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Area of Identifying the Main Ideas According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	T	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	67.71	0.023	0.982	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	39	67.63				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	35	68.93	0.598	0.551	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	52	66.83				
Distance from Home to School	Near	32	65.63	-0.909	0.366	0.05	Not Significant
	Far	55	68.86				

Table 5 presents the inferential statistics on the difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of identifying the main ideas when grouped and compared according to variables.

All computed *p*-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the results are not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of identifying the main ideas when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school was accepted.

The result implies that the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of identifying the main ideas does not vary when compared according to their profile backgrounds. This indicates that regardless of differences in gender, socio-economic status, or proximity to school, all grade 3 learners demonstrate similar skills in understanding the main ideas of texts. Gender, average family income, and distance from home to school did not influence learners' ability to identify the main idea of the text they read.

The result is supported by Pinero and Cañedo (2024), who revealed no significant differences in reading comprehension level in identifying main ideas and noting details when comparing sex and average family monthly income. However, it contradicts

Sali's (2023) view on the reading comprehension proficiency of grade school learners in terms of getting the main idea, sequencing events, and noting details. The study found a significant difference in the level of proficiency among the variables.

Table 6

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Area of Making Inferences According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	77.08	-0.103	0.918		Not Significant
	Female	39	77.56				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	35	77.50	0.071	0.943	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	52	77.16				
Distance from Home to School	Near	32	74.61	-0.888	0.377		Not Significant
	Far	55	78.86				

Table 6 summarizes the inferential statistics on the difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of making inferences when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-values for variables are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in making inferences when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school was accepted.

The finding indicates no variation in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of making inferences when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school. This suggests that factors such as gender, socio-economic status, and proximity to school do not significantly influence the ability of these learners to make inferences while reading. The result aligns with that of Agabon (2020), revealing no significant difference in the level of comprehension skills of learners in making inferences when compared according to their profile variables.

Table 7

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Area Understanding Vocabulary According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	T	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	55.99	-0.150	0.881		Not Significant
	Female	39	56.41				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	35	55.71	-0.273	0.785	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	52	56.49				
Distance from Home to School	Near	32	55.08	-0.604	0.547		Not Significant
	Far	55	56.82				

Table 7 reviews the inferential statistics on the difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of understanding vocabulary when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-values for variables are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of understanding vocabulary when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school was accepted.

The results imply that the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of understanding vocabulary does not differ when compared to sex, average family monthly income, or distance from home to school. This indicates that factors such as gender, family income, and proximity to school do not significantly impact the vocabulary comprehension abilities of grade

3 learners. Reading teachers can focus on improving reading skills without concern for these demographic variables. The result is supported by Bohol (2024), revealing no significant difference in the level of reading comprehension of learners in vocabulary when compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Table 8

Reading Comprehension Level of Grade 3 Learners in the Area of Determining Supporting Details According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	48	63.28	-0.277	0.783	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	39	64.10				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	35	63.93	0.155	0.877	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	52	63.46				
Distance from Home to School	Near	32	61.72	-1.003	0.319	0.05	Not Significant
	Far	55	64.77				

Table 8 examines the inferential statistics on the difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of determining supporting details when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-values for variables are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of determining supporting details when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school was accepted.

The finding indicates that there was no variation in the reading comprehension level of grade 3 learners in the area of determining supporting details when grouped and compared according to sex, average family monthly income, and distance from home to school. This suggests that factors such as gender, family income, and proximity to school do not significantly influence the ability of third graders to identify supporting details in texts. Reading teachers may need to focus on other variables or instructional methods to improve reading comprehension. The result is supported by Lestari et al. (2017), who revealed no significant difference in students' skills in identifying supporting details in reading. The students have the same knowledge in identifying supporting details from the text they read.

CONCLUSION

The study found that most Grade 3 respondents—primarily male learners from low-income families living near the school—could read with teacher support but were not yet independent readers, and overall, their reading comprehension across all areas remained at the instructional level. When grouped by sex, family income, and home-to-school distance, learners consistently showed the same instructional-level performance, with no significant differences across these variables, indicating that demographic factors did not influence or predict reading comprehension outcomes. The conclusions highlight that learners' comprehension levels were shaped by moderate skills in identifying main ideas, making inferences, and understanding vocabulary, as well as limited exposure to varied reading materials, but their performance remained uniform across all comprehension areas.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these results, the study recommends implementing structured daily reading activities, focused interventions for struggling readers, increased access to diverse reading materials, instruction tailored to learners' backgrounds, ongoing monitoring and recognition of progress, active classroom engagement, parental support at home, continuous teacher training, and expanded future research involving broader contexts and variables.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to the conduct, authorship, and publication of this research. All procedures and interpretations were performed independently, and no financial, professional, or personal relationships influenced the results of this study.

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